

D8.4 REPORT ON NLP RELATIONAL EXTRACTION (REX)

Authors: Julie M. Birkholz, Tess Dejaeghere, Els Lefever,
Pranaydeep Singh, Salvador Ros Muñoz
Date: February 28, 2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004984

Project Acronym: CLS INFRA

D8.5 REPORT ON APPLIED NLP SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

Project Full Title: Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure

Grant Agreement No.: 101004984

Deliverable/Document Information

Deliverable No.: D8.4

Deliverable Title: REX

Authors: Julie M. Birkholz, Tess Dejaeghere, Els Lefever, Pranaydeep Singh, Salvador Ros Muñoz

Dissemination Level: PUBLIC

Document History

Version/Date	Changes/Approval	Author/Approved by
28/02/2025		

The following report documents the work of Work Package 8 in the CLS Infrastructure Project. The general goals of this work package are to increase the ease of access and application to NLP tools, including for less-well-resourced languages, as well as their standardization.

The report is organized as follows: an explanation of relational extraction as a method, and a proposed tool for this task. This tool, in the form of a notebook builds on the NER tools presented in D8.3. These tools integrate work in both WP 6 and 7 which facilitates integration of the pipeline from data preparation, programmable corpora, to analysis and back.

The use of computational tools to identify relations between named entities in text is referred to as Relational Extraction (REX) in computer science, but its use crosses disciplines. REX was developed as a set of techniques from NLP and information retrieval, traditionally implementing rule based systems to infer relations between entities. In CLS WP8 we aimed to further refine computational relational extraction by identifying co-occurrences between named entities at a number of different levels: sentence, correspondence (i.e. sender–receiver), and between/across documents in a corpus. To implement this task we employ a generative AI approach using a RAG system to identify relations. The system first implements a NER task, see D8.3, and there following co-occurrence.

The advent of Large Language Models (LLMs) has significantly advanced the field of Digital Humanities (DH), offering researchers the ability to interact with pre-trained models without the need to develop or train them. This interaction paradigm facilitates complex tasks such as Information Extraction (IE), where the goal is to convert unstructured text into structured data by identifying entities and the relationships between them. However, the application of LLMs in literary-historical research presents unique challenges, notably the models' static nature and their propensity for generating hallucinations—outputs which seem plausible in form, but are factually incorrect. LLMs are trained on extensive datasets which may not encompass the most recent research findings or contemporary discourse, rendering them static and potentially outdated. This limitation is particularly problematic in literary-historical contexts, where accuracy and the production of historically correct information are paramount to justify the use of this tool in CLS contexts. Moreover, LLMs have a tendency to produce hallucinations, generating information which appears credible but lacks factual basis. In the realm of information extraction, such hallucinations can lead to inaccurate outputs along both the historical and factual axes, posing significant challenges for researchers.

These challenges supported the rationale behind the creation of a prototype for relation extraction utilizing Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG). RAG enhances LLMs by incorporating an external retrieval mechanism that supplies relevant, up-to-date information to the model during the generation process. This approach involves constructing a vector database comprising current and pertinent texts related to the research focus. The database is segmented into manageable chunks, each represented as vectors in a high-dimensional space. When a query is made, the system retrieves the most relevant chunks based on vector similarity, providing the LLM with accurate information to ground its responses. This method may mitigate hallucinations, and at the same time ensures that the model's outputs are aligned with the latest research and data (Tonmoy et al., 2024). In theory, the process of collecting background information to query a corpus mirrors the methodologies employed by historians and literary scholars, who gather extensive contextual data to inform their analyses of a text. By utilizing a background corpus as

a vector database, our RAG-based system aligns with traditional research practices on a meta-level, nudging the models' output towards more factual and contextually relevant results. The retrieval mechanism could aid in providing the necessary factual grounding for the generative model, for example to support the creation of large high-quality silver-labeled datasets in CLS, as.

The prototype demonstrates the feasibility and advantages of applying Retrieval-Augmented Generation to relation extraction tasks in literary-historical research, and could be a starting ground for more research in this domain. By addressing the challenges of static knowledge and hallucinations inherent in LLMs, this approach offers a promising pathway for integrating advanced AI techniques into the Digital Humanities, fostering more accurate and insightful analyses and uncovering the application range of LLMs.

By integrating a retrieval mechanism with the generative capabilities of gpt-4o, at the time of writing one of the most powerful generative LLMs, the system can in theory identify and extract relationships between entities within a text more accurately when compared to its zero-shot capabilities. Apart from the letters, we use the biographical information, collected and written out by the domain experts of the Guido Gezelle project, about all people mentioned in the letters as a use-case to show how to populate a vector database with chromadb. The retrieval component ensures that the generative model is informed by this historically accurate information, thereby theoretically reducing the likelihood of hallucinations and untruths. We show users how to evaluate the retrieval component's performance using metrics such as mean average precision, which measure the accuracy and completeness of the retrieved information. These evaluations are tailored to our specific research goals, focusing on the correctness and usefulness of the extracted relations.

Figure 1: schematic overview of the RAG-informed REX pipeline

As visualized in **Figure 1**, our pipeline works as follows:

1. Input:

- A dataframe of letters, where each row includes the letter's text, sender, and receiver.
- Additional context from a collection of documents and an annotation guide specifying the relationships.

2. Processing:

- For each letter:
 - Identify relevant documents for the sender and receiver in the letter, feed them to the prompt through a RAG-approach.
 - Using the language model gpt-4o by OpenAI, extract relationships (in our case, these were SCHOOL, FRIEND, ACQUAINTANCE, LITERARY CONNECTION, CHURCH and FAMILY) and **explanations by the model** about why those relationships were inferred.
 - If there are multiple letters from the same interlocutors, concatenate the relationship labels.

- Save additional metadata from relevant extracted documents.

3. Output:

- A new dataframe with the extracted relationships, explanations by the generative language model, and metadata added as columns.

4. Evaluation:

- Compares the extracted relationships to true relationships to calculate mean average precision, which measures the accuracy and relevance of texts fetched from the chromadb vector database.

5. Visualisation

- Based on the explanations requested and generated by the model, we show users how to create a WordCloud with relevant information which can be used to indirectly interpret what it based its decisions on.
- Secondly, we show users how to create a network visualization with the [Pyvis](#) Python library.

We aimed to **create Jupyter notebooks** to demystify pipelines and **inspire** users to **re-use, adapt and improve** these methodologies for their own use-cases.

Best practices

This notebook is a prototype for a RAG-driven relation extraction system which works on multilingual letters (English, French, Dutch) and focuses on the interlocutors. Remember that this prototype uses a paid closed-source LLM (ChatGPT) to establish a performance ceiling and showcase a possible approach to REX. This is only one of the many ways to conduct relation extraction, and the approach should be further adapted and tested across models and use-cases.

Relation extraction prototype with GenAI (OpenAI) and RAG

Version

Given that the deliverables are published as Jupyter Notebooks, the version information depends on the installed Python packages:

chromadb	0.6.3
google	NA
langchain_core	0.3.30
langchain_openai	NA
langchain_text_splitters	NA
openai	1.59.6

IPython 7.34.0
jupyter_client 6.1.12
jupyter_core 5.7.2
notebook 6.5.5

Python 3.11.11

Version Date

20/01/2025

Which Operating Systems does it work on?

- Windows
- Unix
- MacOS
- Linux

License

- Fully free (Chromadb)
- Commercial (OpenAI)

Distribution

- Cloud service

Where to download, how to install, documentation, user guides

- <https://github.com/GhentCDH/CLSinfra/tree/main> all information regarding the literary-historical annotations of the travel literature dataset, the Python packages, and the rationale behind the creation of the notebooks can be found on our GitHub which gets updated regularly.

User interface

- GUI
- API-REST

Docker instance

- Yes

How does the tool process your text?

- Automatically adds some labels (relationship annotation) to your texts.

Does the tool allow you to export the results?

- Yes

Is this tool a statistical model (or a set thereof)?

- No

Does this tool include statistical models? (Irrelevant, erase if this is a statistical model)

- No

Can you easily train and use your own statistical model with this tool ?

- No

XML-TEI compatibility

- The tool does not support XML-TEI at all.

How is an input document to be structured for the tool?

Given that this tool is a Jupyter Notebook showcasing a possible NLP-pipeline for REX, the way the input text is structured to apply the relationship extraction should be adapted to researchers' own purposes. The data we use is the result of the Guido Gezelle Project, a digitization effort aimed at creating a digital collection of letters to and from Gezelle – a famous Flemish poet, priest and writer from the 19th century who wrote in multiple languages. Our approach is two-fold:

- The Notebook takes a dataframe with metadata on the people in the letters (Wikipedia pages, names and person ids) to create a chromadb vector database.
- The Notebook takes a dataframe with the letters and their metadata (letter, sender id, receiver id, annotated relationship labels) to feed to the prompt.

The approach is a showcase and should be adapted to your own data structure and goals.

Methods and features

We use a tool to solve a task. The tool is approaching this task with methods to provide some features or compute values of some metrics for the given text. Features typically enrich the input text (either in-line or stand-off) with labels or filter the text according to a query.

Assigned labels typically belong to a given tagset (e. g. Universal Dependencies or Penn Treebank) or/and pertain to a formalism such as HPSG or minimalist syntax). Filters typically pertain to a query language (also a formalism).

Quick orientation for contributors	Task (what you want to achieve with that method)	Method (usually more generic than task)	Features/ Metric/ Formalism, Tagset
Information extraction	Relational extraction from unstructured text		

Which human languages does the tool support (as of February 2023)?

Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Any (it is language-agnostic)	
Dutch (not Flemish)	
English	
Flemish (not Dutch)	
French	
German	

Which other tools from this list does it integrate?

- Chromadb
- OpenAI

Papers

Tonmoy, S. M. T. I., Zaman, S. M. M., Jain, V., Rani, A., Rawte, V., Chadha, A., & Das, A. (2024). *A Comprehensive Survey of Hallucination Mitigation Techniques in Large Language Models* (No. arXiv:2401.01313). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2401.01313>